

Obsession with Covid-19 Scale (OCS)					
How often have you experienced the following activities over the last 2 weeks ?	Not at all	Rare, less than a day or two	Several days	More than 7 days	Nearly every day over the last 2 weeks
1. I had disturbing thoughts that I may have caught the coronavirus.	0	1	2	3	4
2. I had disturbing thoughts that certain people I saw may have the coronavirus.	0	1	2	3	4
3. I could not stop thinking about the coronavirus	0	1	2	3	4
4. I dreamed about the coronavirus.	0	1	2	3	4
Column totals					
Total Score					

Coronavirus Anxiety Scale (CAS)					
How often have you experienced the following activities over the last 2 weeks ?	Not at all	Rare, less than a day or two	Several days	More than 7 days	Nearly every day over the last 2 weeks
1. I felt dizzy, lightheaded, or faint, when I read or listened to news about the coronavirus	0	1	2	3	4
2. I had trouble falling or staying asleep because I was thinking about the coronavirus	0	1	2	3	4
3. I felt paralyzed or frozen when I thought about or was exposed to information about the coronavirus.	0	1	2	3	4
4. I lost interest in eating when I thought about or was exposed to information about the coronavirus.	0	1	2	3	4
5. I felt nauseous or had stomach problems when I thought about or was exposed to information about the coronavirus.	0	1	2	3	4
Column totals					
Total Score					

Adapted WSAS, a measure of functional impairment

Instructions: Please rate each of the following questions on a 0 to 8 scale: 0 indicates no impairment at all and 8 indicates very severe impairment.

<i>Not at all</i>		<i>Slightly</i>		<i>Definite-ly</i>		<i>Markedly</i>		<i>Very Severely</i>
0	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8

	<i>Questions</i>	<i>Rating scale 0 - 8</i>
1	Because of my fear, anxiety or obsession about coronavirus, my ability to work is impaired. (0 means not at all impaired and 8 means very severely impaired to the point I can't work.)	
2	Because of my fear, anxiety or obsession about coronavirus over the last 2 weeks, my home management (cleaning, tidying, shopping, cooking, looking after home or children, paying bills) is impaired. (0 means not at all impaired and 8 means very severely impaired.)	
3	Because of my fear, anxiety or obsession about coronavirus over the last 2 weeks, my social leisure activities (with other people, such as parties, bars, clubs, outings, visits, dating, home entertainment) are impaired. (0 means not at all impaired and 8 means very severely impaired.)	
4	Because of my fear, anxiety or obsession about coronavirus over the last 2 weeks, my private leisure activities (done alone, such as reading, gardening, collecting, sewing, walking alone) are impaired. (0 means not at all impaired and 8 means very severely impaired.)	
5	Because of my fear, anxiety or obsession about coronavirus over the last 2 weeks, my ability to form and maintain close relationships with others, including those I live with, is impaired. (0 means not at all impaired and 8 means very severely impaired.)	